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OPTIMIZING MILITARY LOGISTICS MANAGEMENT AND ENGINEERING TO SUPPORT THE FREE NUTRITIOUS MEAL (MBG) PROGRAM: AN INTEGRATIVE STRATEGIC APPROACH TO CIVIL MILITARY LOGISTICS IN THE DEMOGRAPHIC BONUS ERA

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Abstract:

Background: In early 2025, the Government of Indonesia launched the Free Nutritious Meal (MBG) Program to provide nutritious meals for vulnerable populations, including school-aged children, toddlers, and pregnant women across 26 provinces from Aceh to Papua. The Indonesian National Armed Forces (TNI) have been mobilized to support the program through the deployment of 351 Military District Commands (Kodim), 14 Main Naval Bases (Lantamal), and 41 Air Force Bases (Lanud) to facilitate the distribution of food supplies, particularly in remote and hard-to-reach areas. **Purpose:** This study aims to examine the strategic integration of logistics and interagency collaboration in supporting the successful implementation of the MBG Program as a long-term national investment in nutrition and human capital development. **Methodology:** A qualitative research design was employed, utilizing a literature-based approach with deductive analysis to explore the logistical framework and institutional coordination involved in the program's implementation. **Results:** The findings highlight that the primary challenge of the MBG Program lies in establishing an effective and sustainable supply chain management system at a national scale. Ensuring the equitable distribution of nutritious meals to tens of millions of beneficiaries requires a logistics infrastructure that is integrated, efficient, and resilient. Key issues identified include inadequate infrastructure, complex archipelagic geography, limitations in local supply chains, and fragmented inter-agency coordination. **Implications:** Addressing these challenges necessitates the development of professional human resources and organizational structures capable of managing the program efficiently. Strengthened collaboration between civilian institutions (relevant ministries and local governments) and TNI logistical units is crucial to achieving operational success.

Keywords: Logistics Management, Supply Chain Optimization, Nutrition Program, Military-Civil Collaboration, Public Health Policy

1. Introduction

The Free Nutritious Meal (MBG) Program is a strategic initiative launched by the Government of Indonesia in early 2025, aiming to provide free nutritious meals to vulnerable groups, including school-aged children, toddlers, and pregnant women across 26 provinces from Aceh to Papua. In its implementation, the Indonesian National Armed Forces (TNI) have been actively involved, deploying 351 Military District Commands (Kodim), 14 Main Naval Bases (Lantamal), and 41 Air Force Bases (Lanud) to support the distribution of food supplies to targeted areas, particularly remote regions.

The urgency of the MBG Program is closely tied to the country's nutritional challenges. Data from the National Population and Family Planning Agency (BKKBN) indicate that the prevalence of stunting in Indonesia decreased from 30.8% in 2018 to 24.4% in 2021. However, this figure remains above the national target of 14% set for 2024. (BKKBN, 2022).

From a public management perspective, the MBG Program adopts a Whole-of-Government (WoG) approach, which emphasizes integrated, cross-agency collaboration in addressing complex public issues. (OECD, 2006) In this context, synergy between civilian logistics actors (such as the Ministry of Health, National Nutrition Agency, and local governments) and military logistics units (TNI) is essential to ensure the successful distribution of nutritious food nationwide. The WoG approach is believed to enhance program effectiveness and reduce the overall cost of public service delivery. (Christensen, T., & Læg Reid, 2007:1059-1066) In addition, the program also incorporates a Whole-of-Nation approach, engaging non-governmental actors, including communities and the private sector, in support of national objectives. (Freeman, R. E., 1984).

The author's empirical experience as a Command and Staff College (Pasis) participant, having served in various TNI logistics units, provides firsthand insights into both the opportunities and challenges of this integration. At the TNI Headquarters Logistics Agency (Babek TNI), procurement and distribution flows are often hindered by bureaucratic processes and overlapping inter-service authorities. In the Iskandar Muda Regional Logistics Unit (Bekangdam) in Aceh, collaboration with local social and health departments has accelerated food aid distribution, albeit in an ad-hoc manner. Meanwhile, in the Garut Regional Logistics Detachment (Denbekang), limitations in warehouse infrastructure and transport fleets have delayed deliveries to rural areas. In Kodam IX/Udayana, information technology is beginning to be applied to monitor inter-island distribution flows, aligning with the broader need for digital transformation in the supply chain. (Wang, Y., & Pettit, S. 2016). These cumulative experiences highlight the gap between the existing logistics conditions within the TNI and the ideal standards required to support integrated civil-military public service delivery.

Therefore, optimizing logistics management and engineering within the TNI is imperative. This includes digitalization, cross-agency governance integration, strengthening of resilient supply chains, adoption of modern technologies, and enhancement of both civilian and military human resource capacity. Such an approach is expected to support the successful implementation of the MBG Program as a strategic nutritional investment for Indonesia's future.

Purpose: This study aims to examine and formulate strategies for optimizing logistics management and engineering within the Indonesian National Armed Forces (TNI) to support the successful implementation of the Free Nutritious Meal (MBG) Program as a national initiative to address nutrition and stunting issues in Indonesia. Specifically, the objectives of this study are to:

1. Analyze the readiness and capabilities of the TNI logistics system in supporting large-scale public service programs, particularly the MBG initiative.
2. Identify challenges and opportunities in the integration between civilian and military logistics, including structural barriers, organizational culture differences, and operational technicalities.
3. Evaluate inter-agency collaboration practices (civil-military cooperation) within the frameworks of the Whole-of-Government (WoG) and Whole-of-Nation (WoN) approaches.
4. Formulate managerial and logistics engineering strategies based on digitalization, resilient supply chains, and strengthened governance to support the effective and efficient implementation of the MBG Program, particularly in the context of Indonesia's demographic bonus.

Methods & Approaches: This study employs a qualitative approach based on library research, aimed at analyzing and developing a theoretical understanding of civil-military logistics integration in supporting public service programs, with a particular focus on the Free Nutritious Meal (MBG) Program. The study adopts a deductive reasoning model, beginning with general theoretical frameworks on military logistics, public supply chain management, and the Whole-of-Government and Whole-of-Nation approaches. These frameworks are then specifically analyzed to understand the implementation context of the MBG Program in Indonesia. The deductive approach enables the researcher to assess the relevance and applicability of these conceptual models to real-world dynamics, based on findings from existing literature.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1 Legal Basis

Law No. 34 of 2004 on the Indonesian National Armed Forces (TNI): The optimization of TNI logistics within the MBG Program can be linked to the role of Military Operations Other Than War (OMSP), particularly in the distribution of food supplies to underdeveloped, frontier, and outermost (3T) regions.

Presidential Regulation No. 72 of 2021 on the Acceleration of Stunting Reduction: Synergy between the TNI and civilian institutions in the distribution of nutritious food can reinforce the implementation of this policy. (Pemerintah Republik Indonesia, 2021).

Law No. 59 of 2024 on the National Long-Term Development Plan (RPJPN) 2025–2045: This law emphasizes the importance of utilizing local production, including regional food sources, in national development. The integration of TNI logistics can support the distribution of local food across Indonesia, in line with the RPJPN vision. (Pemerintah Republik Indonesia, 2024).

Presidential Regulation No. 66 of 2020 on the National Food Agency: Collaboration between the National Food Agency and the TNI can strengthen the food supply chain within the MBG Program. (Badan Pangan Nasional, 2020)

Law No. 23 of 2014 on Regional Government: Synergy between the TNI and local governments can facilitate the smooth distribution of nutritious food to all corners of the country. (Pemerintah Republik Indonesia, 2014)

2.2 Theoretical

Operational Naval Logistics Theory – Henry E. Eccles. (Eccles, H. E., 1959) The concept of *Operational Naval Logistics*, as developed by Henry E. Eccles—a Rear Admiral in the U.S. Navy and logistics scholar—emphasizes the importance of logistics as an integral component of military strategy. Eccles’ theory emerged in the aftermath of World War II, when it became evident that the Allies’ logistical superiority (in terms of ammunition, food, equipment, and fuel supplies) was a decisive factor in achieving victory. The core principles of Eccles’ theory relevant to this study are twofold: (1) the critical need for inter-agency synchronization to support logistics requirements (since logistics is not solely a military concern but also involves the national economic and industrial sectors); and (2) the effectiveness of logistics is measured by how well it extends the *operational reach* of forces in the field.

Supply Chain Operations Reference (SCOR) Model – APICS. (APICS, 2017). The SCOR Model is a standardized framework for supply chain management developed by the Supply Chain Council (now part of APICS/ASCM) since 1996. It provides standardized processes, performance metrics, best practices, and technologies for managing end-to-end supply chains. The SCOR model divides the supply chain into six core processes: Plan, Source, Make, Deliver, Return, and Enable. Its primary advantage lies in offering a common language and standardized performance metrics that enable organizations to benchmark and diagnose their supply chain performance.

In essence, the SCOR model enriches the analytical foundation of this study with a holistic (end-to-end) and quantitative (metrics-based) perspective of modern supply chain management. While the model originates in the private sector, its principles remain highly applicable in the context of non-profit, large-scale public service programs such as MBG.

The Resilient Enterprise – Supply Chain Resilience by Yossi Sheffi. (Sheffi, Y, 2005). In *The Resilient Enterprise: Overcoming Vulnerability for Competitive Advantage* (2005), Yossi Sheffi argues that supply chain resilience is defined by the ability to absorb shocks, adapt, and recover rapidly from disruptions. Within the MBG framework, Sheffi’s concept is applied through the evaluation of the Supply Chain

Resilience Index (SCRI) in the MBG-TNI logistics network. Soni et al. (2014) proposed a quantitative model of SCRI that integrates various resilience enablers into a single numerical index. This index takes into account factors such as redundancy (stockpiles, alternative routes), visibility (flow tracking), flexibility (contracts and systems), collaboration (partner integration), and market position.

SCRI enables organizations to assess the effectiveness of their risk mitigation strategies and compare their supply chain resilience with industry benchmarks. Sheffi's theory thus offers a long-term perspective on the durability and performance of the MBG logistics system, complementing the short-term efficiency focus of the SCOR model. Both aspects are crucial—supply chains must be both efficient and resilient. In the TNI's strategic planning to support MBG, resilience should be treated as a key performance indicator alongside routine distribution metrics.

Whole-of-Government (WoG) Approach – OECD. (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 2006). The Whole-of-Government (WoG) approach is a governance concept that emphasizes cross-sector and cross-agency collaboration to provide comprehensive solutions to complex issues. The OECD (2006) defines WoG as a strategy in which governments actively utilize formal and informal networks to coordinate policy interventions across agencies, aiming to enhance overall effectiveness. WoG emerged as a response to bureaucratic silos that often fragmented public programs. Through WoG, coherence in decision-making and policy implementation is expected.

In the MBG context, elements of the WoG approach are already evident—for instance, Presidential Decree No. 72/2021 on the Acceleration of Stunting Reduction appoints the National Population and Family Planning Agency (BKKBN) as a cross-sector coordinator. Since MBG is a component of stunting reduction efforts, it operates within this coordination framework. However, WoG implementation often faces challenges such as organizational culture differences, sectoral egos, disparate accountability schemes, and disincentives for budget sharing. Therefore, WoG requires strong leadership (a top-down directive) and a clear framework for task distribution.

Stakeholder Theory – R. Edward Freeman. (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 2006). Stakeholder Theory was introduced by R. Edward Freeman in his 1984 book *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. Although rooted in the business domain, the theory carries broader implications: organizations should be managed by considering the interests of all parties affected by their actions (stakeholders), not just owners or shareholders. Stakeholders include both internal groups (employees, management) and external ones (customers, suppliers, communities, governments, etc.).

Public Value Chain & Public Value Creation – Mark Moore. (Moore, M. H, 1995). Mark H. Moore of the Harvard Kennedy School introduced the concept of *Public Value* in public management through his book *Creating Public Value: Strategic Management in Government* (1995). Moore draws an analogy between public managers and corporate managers: both are tasked with creating value, but in the public sector, this refers to *public value* rather than profit. One of the analytical tools introduced by Moore is the *public value chain*, an adaptation of Michael Porter's value chain for the public sector

Digital Supply Chain Transformation – Yingli Wang. (Wang, Y., & Pettit, S. 2016). In *Supply Chain Transformation: Emerging Technologies for Sustainable Growth*, Yingli Wang emphasizes that digital transformation is not merely about investing in software or hardware; it also involves transforming capabilities and business models. Organizations must develop new skills and innovative operating models to fully harness the benefits of technology in supply chains.

3. Methodology

This research adopts a qualitative research design was employed, utilizing a literature-based approach with deductive analysis to explore the logistical framework and institutional coordination involved in the program's implementation. Data and findings are analyzed by triangulation between the above approaches, so that a complete understanding is produced that is able to answer the focus of the discussion. The writing process follows scientific academic standards; each argument is supported by valid evidence or references. The final result is expected to be a balanced strategic policy paper and can be used as a reference for decision making at the national level.

4. Analysis and Discussion

4.1 Analysis

In qualitative research based on library research, data analysis is conducted using an interpretive, critical, and thematic approach. The following is the general structure of the data analysis method used in qualitative library studies:

1. **Collection of Secondary Data (Literature Sources):** This involves identifying and gathering relevant sources such as books, scholarly journals, policy documents, official reports, articles, and other publications.
2. **Data Reduction:** This is the process of selecting essential information from the collected documents or literature, focusing only on content that is relevant to the research objectives.
3. **Conclusion Drawing and Verification:** This involves synthesizing the overall findings from the literature and formulating conclusions based on thematic patterns, while also verifying the consistency and relevance of the interpretations.

4.2 Discussion

Lack of an Integrated MBG Logistics Information System (Low Digitalization)

Currently, the logistics information system supporting the Free Nutritious Meal Program (MBG) remains manual, fragmented, and unintegrated across relevant agencies. The low level of digitalization leads to weak supply chain visibility, inaccurate data, and delays in the distribution of nutritious food. The proposed solution is to develop a *National MBG Logistics Dashboard* based on civil-military integration. The implementation strategy includes forming a joint IT task force from the TNI (Indonesian Armed Forces' Data and Information Center) and the Ministry of Communication and Information/BSSN to design a secure (mil-grade encryption), yet user-friendly system for civilian use; phased development (pilot projects in selected regions before national rollout); gradual integration of multi-stakeholder data (recipient data from Ministry of Education, supply data from BULOG, TNI kitchen info, etc.) into a single data lake; and user training at all levels. The system should be modular, including planning, distribution, and monitoring/reporting modules. TNI can contribute disciplined experience in centralized information systems (e.g., adapting the existing TNI WCC – Warrior Command Center – concept to the MBG dashboard). Supporting technologies such as QR codes or RFID for distribution package tracking will also be adopted.

Fragmented Logistics Governance (Lack of Civil-Military Coordination Integration). The solution is to establish joint coordination and regulatory mechanisms. Strategies include drafting cross-agency standard operating procedures (SOPs) from the central to local levels for MBG logistics operations; establishing joint command posts at each level (national, provincial, district) composed of military and civilian representatives (e.g., at the provincial level, led by the Head of the Food Agency with a Korem officer as deputy); and conducting regular coordination meetings. In addition, alignment of sectoral regulations will be pursued—such as revising BULOG policies to allow direct rice delivery to TNI kitchens or schools, or signing MOUs between the Ministry of Home Affairs and the TNI on the joint use of regional and military assets. Integrated performance management will also be implemented: key performance indicators (KPIs) of the MBG program will be agreed upon across institutions, ensuring all stakeholders work toward the same targets (e.g., KPI: percentage of subdistricts with daily distribution coverage).

Vulnerability and High Costs in the MBG Food Supply Chain. The MBG food supply chain is vulnerable to disruptions such as supply instability, extreme weather, or distribution challenges in remote areas. Consequently, logistics costs are high due to inefficient routing, lack of consolidation, and high risk management expenses. In his theory of the *Resilient Enterprise*, Sheffi asserts that supply chain resilience is essential to ensure service continuity under uncertainty. (Sheffi, Y. 2005)

The central and local governments should initiate an *MBG Food Supply Resilience Strengthening Program*, for instance through ministerial regulations or joint circular letters (by the Minister of Home Affairs, Minister of Agriculture, and Head of the National Food Agency) mandating supply chain risk mitigation measures. Policies include the development of dedicated MBG food reserves, diversification of supply sources, and local community participation. The main goal is to ensure uninterrupted daily delivery of nutritious meals regardless of seasonal, geographical, or other disruptions.

Limited Adoption of Modern Technology and Practices (Need for Digital Logistics Transformation). MBG faces limitations in adopting advanced digital technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Big Data Analytics, or Blockchain in logistics management. Digital transformation is necessary to enhance productivity, distribution speed, and adaptability to changes. According to APICS's SCOR Model,

digitalization across the entire Plan-Source-Make-Deliver-Return cycle is essential to improve supply chain performance (APICS, 2017).

For MBG, the first step is digitization—converting manual records into electronic formats (via the dashboard outlined in Point 1). The second step is digitalization—integrating functions (e.g., the planning module connects to procurement, so once menus are set, the system automatically informs BULOG of material needs). The third is full transformation—applying smart technologies.

Limited Capacity and Synergy of TNI and Civilian Human Resources in Logistics (Human Capital Issue). The capacity of both TNI and civilian personnel in managing MBG logistics remains limited in terms of technical competence, technology adoption, and collaboration skills. This lack of synergy hampers operational effectiveness on the ground. Eccles, in his *Operational Naval Logistics* theory, emphasizes that successful military logistics depends heavily on the sustained competence, training, and coordination of human resources. (Eccles, H. E. 1959)

The strategy involves enhancing human capacity, capability, and collaboration through education, training, exchange, and institutional culture. *Education* involves embedding civil-military logistics integration topics in formal education programs such as TNI staff colleges or civil service training. *Training* refers to joint technical and managerial programs (e.g., integrated supply chain management courses, joint logistics simulation exercises). *Exchange* entails structured personnel rotation: TNI officers interning in civilian agencies (BULOG, Food Agency) for 6–12 months, and civilian/public enterprise logistics staff placed in TNI units for the same period. This mirrors cross-agency *On-the-Job Training (OJT)* programs.

Action Plan

- a) Issue a national policy on MBG logistics digitalization.
- b) Implement concrete measures, including:

Application Development – build a dashboard app/web platform within 6–12 months in partnership with state-owned enterprises or defense IT industries (e.g., PT Telekomunikasi, PT LEN) to ensure technological sovereignty.

Training and Socialization – conduct nationwide training for local logistics administrators and TNI units on dashboard usage; create manuals and help centers.

Data Integration Workshops – hold technical workshops across agencies to harmonize data formats and interoperability protocol.

Trial & Evaluation – run live pilots in five provinces, gather bug reports and user feedback, then scale up nationally.

Maintenance & Security – designate a responsible unit (e.g., Ministry Data Center or Army’s Signal Corps) for daily operations and form a joint cybersecurity team to safeguard the system. This effort is expected to produce a robust digital system that enhances transparency and speed within the MBG supply chain while preventing issues such as double reporting or lost distribution tracking.

- c) Establishing Institutional Policy for the Formation of an Integrated MBG Logistics Command /Management System. Concrete actions include:

Declaring the MBG Task Force/Agency – appointing core management and a joint secretariat, complete with terms of reference for each role.

Developing an Integrated SOP – holding cross-agency workshops with experts to formulate an integrated logistics SOP (from menu planning, material supply, to handling field complaints).

Simulations and Drills – conducting periodic end-to-end logistics simulations (e.g., quarterly) to test coordination, involving all stakeholders, similar to a fire drill to detect coordination issues early

Command Center – establishing a national command center (which can utilize existing facilities like the BNPB Crisis Center or TNI’s Puskodal) to operate 24/7, monitoring program execution, equipped with monitoring screens (eventual integration with the digital dashboard)

Strengthening Regulations – formulating and ratifying necessary agreements or technical guidelines, such as the Ministry of Home Affairs’ technical guidelines requiring governors and regents to involve local military units in the regional implementation team. These efforts aim to ensure that what was once siloed governance becomes closely connected, with a clear chain of command while respecting the civil sector as the program leader.

d) Issuing Supply Chain Resilience Policy for MBG. Concrete efforts include:

Local Community Kitchen Program – expanding community kitchens jointly managed by TNI and local communities (schools, NGOs), with at least one in each sub-district, supported by TNI equipment and volunteer labor. Currently, TNI targets establishing 96 community kitchens if budget permits, and efforts will ensure this target is met and expanded as needed.

Building Buffer Warehouses – constructing or designating storage warehouses in each military district or strategic location to store food stocks for 1-2 weeks, with a rotation system to ensure fresh supplies. The TNI's Army Combat Engineers or logistics company can manage these buffer warehouses.

Farmer and SME Partnerships – implementing a partnership program where local farmer groups and food SMEs supply ingredients to MBG with off-take contracts, ensuring shorter supply chains and stable markets for farmers. TNI will assist through Babinsa to ensure quality and continuity.

Route and Fleet Optimization – applying route optimization methods (with GIS software) to determine the most efficient daily delivery routes, combining fleets from local governments, TNI, and possibly third parties. Preventive maintenance for TNI fleets (trucks, naval ships, etc.) will also be conducted to ensure operational readiness.

Monitoring and Quality Control – forming a joint supply chain oversight team (including ALI, BPOM, and the food agency) responsible for conducting surprise inspections at kitchens and distribution routes to ensure SOPs are followed. They will also monitor resilience indicators like fill rate, lead time, and food damage rates at delivery points. These efforts aim to make the MBG supply chain resilient while cutting costs through reduced travel distances and bureaucratic layers.

e) Formulating a Policy for Digital Transformation of Defense and Civil Logistics. Concrete steps:

IT Infrastructure Investment – strengthening internet networks at TNI bases and schools, possibly with satellite or military radio networks, to ensure connectivity is not a barrier. Providing devices (tablets/laptops) for each sub-district command post.

Training of Trainers (ToT) – training a group of joint military-civilian instructors who will then train peers in the field, speeding up the spread of knowledge and new standards.

Assignments and Career Pathways – establishing rules (e.g., 5% of positions in central and regional food agencies can be filled by active TNI officers, in line with the revised TNI Law) for a limited time, with a clear career path upon returning to their units. Similarly, civilian talents can be recruited into military units as civil servants specializing in logistics.

Competitions and Appreciation – holding performance or innovation contests among regional MBG logistics teams, with winners receiving recognition from the TNI Commander and relevant ministers.

Welfare and Morale – ensuring the welfare of field personnel (both military and civilian), e.g., providing extra meal allowances or rewards for those working in difficult areas, and ensuring task rotation to prevent burnout. These efforts aim to produce outstanding human resources that are professionally skilled in logistics and solid in team relationships. TNI and civilian personnel will increasingly understand one another—military personnel will appreciate the accountability of civil administration processes, while civilians will understand the military's discipline and rapid response ethos—creating harmony in collaboration. In the long term, investment in human capital will ensure the continuity of integration: even with advanced technology or structures, without competent personnel, integration will not reach its full potential.

5. Conclusion

- a) Based on the analysis in Chapters I to VI, it can be concluded that the Free Nutritious Meal Program (MBG) is a national strategic step to optimally utilize Indonesia's demographic bonus. By 2030, it is estimated that about 70% of Indonesia's population will be under 40 years old, a great potential that must be supported by improving human resource quality from an early age. The MBG program was born as a transformative effort to improve the nutritional status of children and vulnerable groups, so that the younger generation, who will be the backbone of defense and development, will have excellent physical and mental capacities. This program is not only a social policy but also a long-term investment for national resilience in the field of human resources.
- b) The analysis shows that the main challenge of MBG lies in how to manage an effective and sustainable logistics supply chain on a massive scale across the archipelago. Distributing nutritious

food to tens of millions of recipients evenly requires an integrated, efficient, and reliable national logistics system. The lack of infrastructure, the archipelagic geographic condition, limited local supply chains, and inter-agency coordination are crucial issues identified in this study. This is where the role of the TNI, particularly the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL), is seen as a strategic force multiplier in logistics. The TNI AL has an extensive network of bases and naval transportation fleets, which, when integrated with the civilian logistics system, will strengthen distribution reach to 3T areas (underdeveloped, outermost, and frontier regions). This aligns with Henry E. Eccles' thinking that logistics plays a strategic role in strengthening a country's defense system, both in times of peace and war. In other words, military involvement in supporting non-military programs like MBG is not only a form of Military Operations Other Than War (OMSP) but also an investment in long-term national resilience through improving the nutrition and health of the younger generation.

- c) This KKA study concludes that the integrated planning of human resources and logistics engineering is the key to the success of MBG. From the HR perspective, the preparation of personnel and organizations capable of professionally running the program is needed, including collaboration between civil agencies (relevant ministries/institutions, local governments) and TNI logistics units. From the logistics engineering side, it is necessary to design an end-to-end supply chain system that optimally utilizes national infrastructure—starting with the procurement of food materials from producers (especially involving MSMEs, local farmers, and fishermen), storage in strategic warehouse facilities, and ending with distribution to schools and posyandus across the region. Integration of logistics information systems is also necessary so that the flow of goods, information, and funds can be controlled in real-time, in accordance with the 2012 National Logistics System Blueprint, which emphasizes the importance of efficiency and security in logistics flows from origin to destination. If all these aspects are managed well, the MBG program is expected to run on target, efficiently, and sustainably. The success of MBG will not only reduce malnutrition and stunting issues but also strengthen Indonesia's food security and national resilience overall.

Recommendations

Strategic Recommendations

1. Strengthening the Role of TNI in the National Logistics System: The TNI Commander needs to enhance the role of TNI as part of the National Logistics System in supporting the MBG program.
2. Defense Policy Supporting Social Programs: The Minister of Defense is expected to formulate policies that bridge non-military programs like MBG with the national defense strategy.
3. Government Commitment and Budget Sustainability: The President of the Republic of Indonesia, as the head of government, must provide clear direction to ensure civil-military integration in the implementation of MBG.

Follow-up Recommendations

1. Disseminating Study Results to Key Stakeholders: Pasis can prepare an executive summary or policy brief of this KKA to be submitted to the TNI Commander and the Ministry of Defense.
2. Encouraging the Formation of a Special Coordination Team: As an action step, pasis can initiate the proposal for the establishment of a national task force or team, consisting of representatives from ministries /institutions and TNI. This team's task will be to formulate an integrated MBG supply chain SOP, including the scheme for utilizing TNI assets for food distribution.
3. Advocacy at the Highest Policy Levels: If pasis has the opportunity to access the president's inner circle (Ring 1)
4. Ongoing Monitoring and Evaluation: Pasis should also be involved or encourage the establishment of a mechanism to evaluate the implementation of recommendations.

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